

UNCOVERING THE IMPACT OF SOCIAL MEDIA INFLUENCER ENDORSEMENTS ON THE PURCHASE INTENTION OF COLLAGEN DRINKS

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ABSTRACT

In the digital era, a kind of popularity has emerged: the social media influencers. Collagen drinks as an innovative alignment in the struggle for convenience in the era of immediate satisfaction and filtered perception. These products, which guaranteed to overtake the market because of the influence of social media influencers. The researchers were enthralled by this aspect, which led them to look into ways social media influencer endorsements are delivered on different platforms like Facebook, Instagram, TikTok, and so on. The aim and objectives of this study looked at the impact of three variables in social media influencers' endorsements on the purchase intention of collagen drinks in wider terms because numerous businesses are investigating this kind of approach to gather their consumers. The basis for this investigation was the Source Credibility Model. People between the ages of 18 and 55 who currently reside in Metro Manila and have watched an influencer endorse collagen drinks were surveyed for the study. Google Forms was used to distribute the survey, and analysis was done on the collected data. The results of the study indicate that three variables perceived expertise, perceived attractiveness, and perceived trustworthiness have an impact on the willingness for making an online purchase. This study found that the potential to purchase collagen drinks is strongly influenced by social media influencer endorsements. The goal of this study is to provide further information regarding social media influencer endorsement and advantages for marketing to academic institutions, business owners, and advertising professionals and students.

Keywords: *Influencer, Collagen, Digital, Endorsements, Intention, Impact*

INTRODUCTION

In the era of digital wellness, social media influencers hold a strong position. Their well-selected internet photos present a picture of enthusiasm and health, complete with disciplined workout routines and glowing skin. And that picture almost always comes with a bottle of collagen drink that they are holding in their hands. Once a specialist supplement tucked away in health food stores, collagen has seen a great rise in popularity thanks in large part to social media influencers' ability to endorse items. These internet influencers have transformed obscure powders into necessary enhancements thanks to their passionate followers and aspirational styles. This study focuses on the Impact of Social Media Influencer Endorsements on Purchase Intention of Collagen Drinks. This study explores the intriguing field of social media influencer marketing and how it affects consumers' intentions to buy collagen drinks in the beauty and wellness sector. In order to comprehend the complex interactions that lead people to buy collagen-based beauty products, the study disentangles the relationships between influencer marketing, collagen trends, and consumer insight. Understanding the complicated nature of this development is essential as social media expands as a platform for famous people and influencers to utilize it to promote collagen-infused drinks and display immaculate skin.

With influencer marketing's growing acceptance among consumers, influencer marketing, however, is a completely new tool and can come with a lot of obstacles that need for creative ways to convey the message. The traditional advertising or celebrity spokesperson models are probably not the same as the influencer marketing model. Companies are realizing that social media influencers have a more significant influence on consumer behavior and are more affordable. Regarding the possible exploitation of this marketing phenomenon by advertisers, there is still a dearth of knowledge. It is imperative to further investigate this phenomenon and offer a more thorough explanation in order to advance our present understanding and promote successful marketing strategies. Through a focus on their function in forming perceptions of consumers, this study intends to investigate the impact of reputation, experience, and the quality of information on consumers' intention to purchase recommended collagen drinks by social media influencers.

This study aims to delve into the influential role of social media influencers in shaping consumer purchase intention within the burgeoning beauty and wellness sector, particularly in the context of collagen drink endorsements. Through a multifaceted investigation, this research seeks to unravel the intricate dynamics between social media influencer endorsements and consumer purchase intention, elucidating the nuanced factors that drive individuals towards purchasing collagen drink-based beauty products. By exploring the persuasive mechanisms at tactics within influencer marketing and their impact on consumer decision-making, this study aspires to provide a comprehensive understanding of how these endorsements sway perceptions, preferences, and intentions in the context of collagen drinks, contributing valuable insights to both academic discourse and industry practices within the beauty and wellness domain. Furthermore, this research aims to bridge the existing gap in scholarly literature by empirically

examining the specific effects of social media influencer endorsements on consumer purchase intention within the collagen drink market. By employing a quantitative research method, this study endeavors to unearth the nuances of influencer marketing strategies, dissecting their effectiveness in shaping consumers' intent to purchase collagen drink-based beauty and wellness products. Ultimately, the objective is to furnish stakeholders in the industry with actionable insights that can inform and enhance marketing strategies, thereby empowering businesses to optimize their use of social media influencers to drive consumer engagement and foster purchase decisions in the competitive landscape of the beauty and wellness industry.

This study found that consumers who were exposed to influencer marketing were more likely to have positive attitudes towards collagen drinks and to believe that they were effective. This research found that social media influencers have a significant impact on purchase intention of collagen drinks among consumer in metro manila from age 18-55. The study found that people in metro manila from age 18-55 who followed and have seen influencers who promoted collagen drinks were more likely to believe that collagen drinks were effective, Social Media Influencer Endorsements can be effective in influencing consumers' attitudes and how they purchase products, including collagen drinks. Influencers can shape public opinion and create a sense of trust and credibility for brands by sharing personal experiences and testimonials. In the help and impact of influencers, they easily get their trust and loyalty of the customers.

Relevant review of related literature supports the researcher's study into the Impact of Social Media Influencer Endorsements on the Purchase Intention of Collagen Drinks. Several studies highlight how influencers affect consumer trust, product marketing, and perceptions of collagen drinks. Mediating factors like predicted brand value and brand involvement have a favorable impact on purchase intention. Tasya Farasya's significant Indonesian Instagram following led to XYZ Cosmetics keeping her on board to shape opinions (Munawaroh & Rudiyanto, 2022). A few key components of a successful product marketing strategy are relatedness, source trustworthiness, and direct relevance. Self-disclosure affects influencers' perceived credibility; appropriateness mitigates this effect (Baptista et al., 2022). The study by Alhothali and Aljefree (2023) added to the body of knowledge on food advertising by characterizing the extent of young people's exposure to food marketing and determining the characteristics that drove young consumers to follow influencers on social media.

In the beauty industry, influencers play a pivotal role in building credibility and trust through social media interactions (Kesner, 2023). Manufacturers of collagen supplements benefit from influencers reaching millions (Collagen by Tosla, 2023). Research on skincare product users in the Philippines indicates that macro-influencers significantly influence purchase decisions and trust (Castaño et al., 2022). Social media serves as a potent tool for skincare marketing, with influencers preferred over celebrities (Lim et al., 2022). Endorser traits such as attractiveness and credibility correlate with purchase decisions (Alayu et al., 2022). Customers' desire to imitate influencers and their online presence are factors that impact brand awareness for start-ups (Bonus et al., 2022).

Influencer advertising is seen favorably by consumers, based on recent studies. Advertising effectiveness and customer purchase intent are highly correlated, with women seeing influencers more favorably. (Bismonte et al., 2021; Alonte et al., 2023) recommends choosing influencers based on their morals, credibility, and personality. The influencer persona directly affects purchase intention, but customer attitude also has a role (Belen et al., 2021). Compared to younger customers, those over 25 exhibited greater caution, valuing the influencer's reliability and expertise (Caysido et al., 2022). Additionally, Castillo et al. (2022) found a substantial correlation among four conjectured factors that influence Filipino Gen Z consumers: credibility, trust, and brand attitude. Influencers, who are viewed as role models, greatly affect the opinions and behavior of their clientele. Organizations can assist customers in weighing the benefits and drawbacks of influencers on social media by promoting media literacy.

Research Questions

In this study, the researchers' objective was to examine the Impact of Social Media Influencer Endorsements on the Purchase Intention of Collagen Drinks. Specifically, the paper aimed to address the following inquiries that the researchers had:

1: What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:

1.1 Sex

1.2 Age

1.3 Location

2: What is the impact of social media influencers endorsement on the purchase intention of Collagen drink in terms of:

2.1 Perceived Expertise

2.2 Perceived Attractiveness

2.3 Perceived Trustworthiness

3: Is there a significant impact of Social Media Influencers Advertisement on the purchasing Intention of a collagen drink?

Based on the theoretical framework and existing literature, the following Hypotheses are proposed for this study:

H₀₁: Perceived expertise has no significant impact on consumers' purchase intention of collagen drink.

H₀₂: Perceived attractiveness has no significant impact on consumers' purchase intention of collagen drink.

H₀₃: Perceived trustworthiness has no significant impact on consumers' purchase intention of collagen drink.

METHODOLOGY

Researchers used a quantitative approach to conduct the investigation. It helps to observe situations that impact the sample population, a specific set of people. In this type of research, a range of methodologies are used to collect diverse numerical data, which are then statistically processed to aggregate, compare, or demonstrate the data. Generally speaking, surveys, studies, and structured observations are instances of quantitative research approaches. (Sreekumar, 2023). To support and achieve the study's objective, the researchers aimed to resolve the aforementioned problem. It also attempted to comprehend the various ways in which social media influencers impact the purchase intention of collagen drinks.

The research paper was worked on in from the ease of the researchers' homes with the aid of several online resources. A modern set of questions that respondents filled on their preferred devices took the place of the usual use of Google Forms. People who now live in Metro Manila were the chosen respondents for the survey required for this study to highlight the investigation's goal, which is to comprehend how social media influencer endorsement affects customers' intention to purchase. Furthermore, the researchers selected the individuals who viewed collagen drink recommendations on social media as study participants because they have a different viewpoint on purchasing and consuming than previous consumers who are unaware of it; these individuals have been termed the most vocal consumers at the moment.

Prior to the survey, the researchers personally approached their family, friends, peers, and acquaintances, a lot on social media through a private message, to ask them to be the respondents in the study. Additionally, the researchers created posts on their Facebook profiles to introduce the study to their mutual' feeds for wider and easier exposure. A consent form guaranteeing the confidentiality and anonymity of the respondents' identities and responses was given before the survey's distribution.

RESULTS

In this section of the study, the collected data from a survey conducted through the Google Forms application is presented. The gathered information underwent thorough presentation, analysis, and interpretation. The findings from the analysis aimed to ascertain the impact of social media influencers on individuals' purchase intention when exposed to advertisements for collagen drinks on social media platforms. This assessment was conducted with a focus on the social media influencers' perceived expertise, perceived attractiveness, and perceived trustworthiness as key factors influencing consumers' purchase intention.

Table 1: Descriptives

Variables	Mean	Standard Deviation
Perceived Expertise	3.05	0.76
Perceived Attractiveness	3.10	0.74
Perceived Trustworthiness	3.04	0.71
Purchase Intention	3.00	0.75

The Table 1 presents descriptive statistics for the study's major variables. Perceived Expertise, Perceived Attractiveness, Perceived Trustworthiness, and Purchase Intention make up the variables. With a mean of 3.05 for perceived expertise, 3.10 for perceived attractiveness, 3.04 for perceived trustworthiness, and 3.00 for purchase intention, the mean values represent the core tendency for each variable. These figures convey that respondents' levels of agreement or impression are moderate. The standard deviations, which indicate the degree of diversity around the mean, for perceived expertise (0.76), perceived attractiveness (0.74), perceived trustworthiness (0.71), and purchase intention (0.75) all show comparatively consistent responses.

Table 2: Linear Regression

Table 2.1: Perceived Expertise

Variable	Pearson correlation	P-value	Regression Coefficient	Decision Rule and Interpretation
Perceived Expertise and Purchase Intention	.836	<.001	.202	Reject Ho: Perceived expertise has no significant impact on consumers' purchase intention.

Customers' purchasing intention is influenced by the perceived expertise of social media influencers, as seen in the Table 2.1. Following the data analysis, a p-value of <0.001 was obtained by using linear regression. The researchers rejected the null hypothesis that "Perceived expertise has no significant impact on consumers' purchase intention" in accordance with the decision rule, which states that the significance difference must be greater than 0.05 in order to accept the null hypothesis. In addition, a very high correlation between the two variables was noted, with a Pearson correlation value of 0.836. This indicates a 0.202 increase in the purchase intention for every unit increase in perceived expertise.

Table 2.2: Perceived Attractiveness

Variable	Pearson correlation	P-value	Regression Coefficient	Decision Rule and Interpretation
Perceived Attractiveness and Purchase Intention	.867	<.001	.256	Reject Ho: Perceived attractiveness has no significant impact on consumers' purchase intention.

The Table 2.2 indicates consumers' purchase intention is affected by the perceived attractiveness of social media influencers. Upon utilizing linear regression for data analysis, a p-value of <0.001 was obtained. Furthermore, a very high correlation between the two variables was found, with a Pearson correlation value of 0.867. The researchers rejected the null hypothesis, which stated, "Perceived attractiveness has no significant impact on consumers' purchase intention," in accordance with the decision rule, which requires a significance level greater than 0.05 to accept the null hypothesis. This shows a 0.256 increase in purchase decisions for every unit increase in perceived attractiveness.

Table 2.3: Perceived Trustworthiness

Variable	Pearson correlation	P-value	Regression Coefficient	Decision Rule and Interpretation
Perceived Trustworthiness and Purchase Intention	.894	<.001	.524	Reject Ho: Perceived trustworthiness has no significant impact on consumers' purchase intention.

The Table 2.3 illustrates the impact of social media influencers' perceived trustworthiness on consumers' purchase intentions. The data interpretation, conducted through linear regression analysis, resulted in a p-value of <0.001. Adhering to the decision rule that stipulates a significance level not less than 0.05 to accept the null hypothesis, the researchers rejected the null hypothesis asserting, "Perceived trustworthiness has no significant impact on consumers' purchase intention." Furthermore, a very high correlation between the two variables was identified, with a Pearson correlation value of 0.894. This reveals a 0.524 increase in purchasing decisions for every unit increase in perceived trustworthiness.

DISCUSSION

The purpose of the study was to determine whether customers' purchase intention was and perceived trustworthiness.

Based on the presented results, the implications for marketers and organizations in the context of social media influencers (SMIs) influencing consumers' purchase intentions were significant. The study's descriptive statistics highlighted moderate means and standard deviations, indicating variability among respondents in key research variables. The subsequent correlation analyses in Tables 2.1, 2.2, and 2.3 demonstrated very highly significant relationships between perceived expertise, perceived attractiveness, perceived trustworthiness, and purchase intention, rejecting all of the null hypotheses. These findings aligned with the existing literature, suggesting that SMIs played a substantial role in shaping consumer attitudes and behaviors.

Building upon the literature review, it was evident that consumers, especially young individuals, derived inspiration and motivation from SMIs who often served as role models and trend-setters. The study's confirmation of the impact of perceived expertise, attractiveness, and trustworthiness on purchase intentions reinforced the significance of these attributes in influencer marketing. Notably, the study contributed by highlighting the mediating variables of brand engagement in self-concept and brand projected value, further emphasizing the importance of brand-related factors in the purchase decision-making process.

The results also underscored the multifaceted nature of influencer marketing, acknowledging the positive and accepting attitudes of consumers toward various advertising effectiveness. Additionally, the study emphasized the role of social media platforms in influencing consumers' purchase intention, supporting the idea that influencers could significantly impact product promotion and brand visibility.

To sum up, organizations that aimed to harness the power of influencer marketing, particularly in the realm of collagen supplements, strategically leveraged influencers' perceived expertise, attractiveness, and trustworthiness. Understanding the mediating role of brand-related variables and recognizing the nuanced aspects of influencer selection could enhance the effectiveness of marketing strategies and contribute to the overall success of products in the highly competitive landscape influenced by social media.

Conclusions

In conclusion, the goal of the current study was to find out how social media influencer endorsements impacted consumers' intentions of purchasing collagen drinks. The results provide significant evidence for the hypothesis that consumers' intentions for purchasing collagen drinks are greatly impacted by the variables that influence social media influencers, notably perceived expertise, perceived attractiveness, and perceived trustworthiness.

Results from the statistical analysis were very significant; the significance value for each variable was less than 0.001. It was discovered that these predictors, along with their impact, explained an important part of the variance in purchase intention, pointing to a strong and credible model. The significance of the independent factors in influencing consumer behavior was further highlighted by the significantly high correlations found between purchase intention and perceived expertise, perceived attractiveness, and perceived trustworthiness. In particular, a 0.202 rise in purchase intention was shown for every unit increase in perceived expertise, based to a Pearson correlation of 0.836. Similarly, for every unit increase in perceived attractiveness, there was a 0.867 increase in purchase intention, which corresponds to a correlation of 0.867. Finally, for every unit increase in perceived trustworthiness, there was a significant 0.524 rise in purchasing intention, in accordance to a Pearson correlation of 0.894. These results highlight the importance of social media influencers and particular aspects of perceived expertise, perceived attractiveness, and perceived trustworthiness that impact consumer

purchasing decisions. They also offer insightful information for businesses and marketers in the collagen drink industry.

Recommendations

The researchers made this study to uncover the impact of social media influencers' endorsements on the purchase intention of collagen drinks with the use of three variables. The findings showed that the endorsements by social media influencers were effective for marketing and advertising, so the researchers proposed that markets and business owners can efficiently utilize the use of social media influencers for marketing campaigns. Business owners can promote their products through social media influencers in order to reach their target market.

Perceived Expertise

- Influencers that fit with a brand's values and intended audience might be chose by businesses. Discover influencers that are a good fit to the business and the target audience. Be specific about the objectives for the influencer campaign. This guarantees that the influencer's endorsement is likely to resonate with the individuals who are most likely interested in the collagen drink.
- Allow the influencer to use their creative skills to market the collagen drink in their own unique way.
- Monitor the campaign's outcomes to determine what is and is not effective.
- The researchers encourage the owners of collagen drink businesses to collaborate with influencers who are known for their proficiency in health and wellness, particularly in skincare or anti-aging, as perceived expertise has a big influence.

Perceived Attractiveness

- TikTok is the most engaging channel to be viewed for social media influencers endorsing a collagen drink; use visually appealing content with influencers supporting or enjoying the drink. Collaborate with influencers who truly approve of collagen drink products and share the brand's beliefs to increase perceived attractiveness.
- Promote openness and disclosure of supported partnerships. Integrate content uploaded by users with endorsements from influencers to establish credibility and social proof.

Perceived Trustworthiness

- The researchers urge collagen drink entrepreneurs to provide incentives in order to increase customer trust and purchase intention. One such incentive may be to give special deals or other incentives through influencer relationships. Additionally, look at more expansive partnership

- opportunities such as collaborating on content, presenting live events, or establishing engagement resources and expanding further sponsorships.
- Transparency and accountability should be given top priority by owners of collagen drink businesses so that clients can make informed decisions about the products they are offering. It might have demonstrated a variety of beneficial qualities that strengthen the influencer's authenticity. Instead of endorsing a collagen drink product, the influencer should talk about their own experiences and encounters using that drink. This lends their endorsement more legitimacy by implying that the promotion is founded on an authentic belief about its efficacy.
 - The influencer could expand on the beneficial effects of each of the specific ingredients in the collagen drink. Customers would be better able to decide whether the product is appropriate for what they need as a result of the product.
 - Regular reminders of the influencer's continuous consumption of the collagen drink would be helpful to support authenticity. Followers may gain important insights regarding potential benefits over time or adjustments in the influencer's viewpoint from this continuous interaction.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Research ethics, a subset of applied ethics, involves well-established principles and norms that specify how exploration is being done because researchers are professionals. Researchers must admire the rights of their subjects and produce high-quality publications of the findings in order to take over ethical exploration in our diurnal lives. In terms of exploration ethics, teleology and deontology are the two most common philosophical seminars (Akaah, 1997). By admitting and crediting the ideas and benefactions of other researchers as well as applying probity, discipline, and the avoidance of error to our disquisition of participated knowledge, the researchers made sure that they upheld ethical norms while also promoting the growth and elaboration of knowledge. The exploration was conducted in agreement with the established guidelines, including brand and patenting regulations, data participating guidelines, and confidentiality rules, to guard intellectual property rights and promote researcher collaboration.

By choosing papers with believable sources and abstain from misconduct actions like fabrication, falsification, plagiarism, and unauthorized use of data that may violate research integrity, distort records, and introduce false information into the system, the researchers manage this research with honesty, trust, responsibility, fairness, respect, and professionalism. Likewise, they would not purposefully avoid, mislead, or attempt to do so by commissioning this research. Here, "misconduct in research" is understood to refer to fabrication, falsification, plagiarism, unauthorized use of data, or other actions that materially depart from the accepted norms within the academic community for proposing, carrying out, or reporting research.

Also, the respondents cared to cleave to the correct exploration protocols in agreement with the most recent norms and format for the field established by the

American Psychological Association (APA) — the 7th Edition. Through it, the authors of this paper swore to no way have reproduced by upholding the law decreeing brand and patent, using proper citations, clinging to proper alphabet and syntax in agreement with the discipline it belongs to, and carrying authorization from the others before using their material as a source for the well- predicated creation. Researchers also verified and made sure that all participants were informed about the proposed research project, including any potential risks and benefits to their physical, psychological, or social state as well as their rights and responsibilities, so that they could make decisions with all the information they required and freely give their consent to participate. Before taking part in the study, subjects must provide their informed consent. The researcher should ask for informed consent from a legally recognized representative when subjects are unable to provide it themselves. Participants should be able to withdraw from a study at any time and for any reason. As long as the researchers themselves took full responsibility, the subjects were free to stop taking part in the study at any time and for any reason. as long as they had the assurance and knowledge necessary to comprehend the general nature of the research. Respect for Persons: Researchers should be considerate of research subjects' rights, dignity, and privacy (Shamoo & Resnik, 2014). Document privacy is important for protecting private information and maintaining trust in many industries. All information, whether personal, financial or business related, must be kept confidential to protect individuals, groups and even society. This article discusses the importance of maintaining document confidentiality, the consequences of data breaches, and preventative measures that can be taken to protect sensitive information.

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But you, be strong and do not lose courage, for there is reward for your work.

2 Chronicles 15:7

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